

A Note on the Estimation of Formic Acid in Commercial Acetate of Lime.

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The gravimetric method described by Auerbach and Zeglin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 103, 167) and the volumetric method suggested by Fouchet (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1912, 11, 323) for the estimation of formic acid, when in aqueous or in acetic acid solutions, were found to give accurate results.

In the case of commercial acetate of lime, however, after decomposing the sample by the method of Fresenius (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1908, 27, 1012), the volumetric method was found to give unreliable results, due to the presence of higher fatty acids and pyroligneous matter in the distillate which hindered the correct end-point of the titration. The gravimetric method on the other hand, gave much more concordant and satisfactory results, and under the present existing methods of estimation, should be preferred.

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